

Is There a Trauma for Researchers? An Exploratory Literature Search About Researcher Trauma

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Purpose

The objective of this study is to discuss traumatic stress experienced by researchers. Researchers can investigate a wide array of research questions involving questions regarding humans who have affected from adverse events (Yilmaz & Karakuş, 2019). Some research studies focus on the trauma experiences. Traumatic stress can be a second-hand or indirect experience due to being intertwined with traumatic content (Yilmaz, 2021). Secondary trauma (Salston & Figley, 2003) and vicarious trauma (Pearlman & Saakvitne, 1995) are the two alternative ways to develop a second-hand experience of trauma. Through the ways of conducting studies about violence, conflict and death (Loyle & Simoni, 2017), doing participant research in a violent places (Autesserre 2014), working in cross cultural settings and feeling guilt and being emotional (Drozdowski & Dominey-Howes, 2015), or by rearing and analysing traumatic narratives (Klocker, 2015), researchers can be exposed to several degrees of traumatic content or can have increased risk for getting traumatized. This new research area is getting attention from diverse disciplines such as political science (Loyle & Simoni, 2017), geography (Drozdowski & Dominey-Howes, 2015), and medicine (Ahmad, 2022). Drozdowski and Dominey-Howes (2015) and Eriksen (2017) explored secondary traumatic stress in researchers and they concluded that researchers can experience somatic complaints such as gastrointestinal problems, sleep problems, loss of appetite and changes in weight, and psychological complaints (increased stress, feeling anxious and/or depressed). They also suggested that more serious situations can develop in researchers as developing post traumatic stress symptoms and committing suicide.

All these researches indicate that researcher trauma is an important issue that requires special attention since traumatic stress not only affect the work of researchers but also researchers'

wellbeing, physical and psychological health (Wood, 2007). From the viewpoint of clinical psychology, the literature regarding researcher trauma will be analyzed within the scope of this presentation/study.

Design

The study will be an exploratory literature review study to shed new light on researcher trauma. What is known about researcher trauma will be summarized out of the existing studies. Since there are a few related studies, a systematic review is not appropriate. After the summarization of the existing knowledge, the contribution of psychology to researcher trauma can be discussed. For instance, the definition, assessment, measurement, treatment and intervention options for researcher trauma can be discussed within the scope of the presentation/study.

Results (if applicable)

My preliminary research in the literature suggests that psychology should be involved more to researcher trauma. Although psychologists and counsellors secondary and vicarious trauma is well appreciated; researcher trauma is still in need of further exploration and help.

Implications

Once researcher trauma is well recognized and acknowledged, more actions are needed to be taken to prevent and treat. For example, as a suggestion, researchers might be trauma-informed by their institutions. or high degree programs (masters and doctorate programs) can offer courses/seminars regarding trauma informed care in the scope of their curriculum.

Resources

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